

Condensation of Butylchloral with Gallic Acid and the Three Cresotic Acids.

By (Miss) B. N. KATRAK AND A. N. MELDRUM.

The study of the condensation of butylchloral, $\text{CH}_3\cdot\text{CHCl}\cdot\text{CCl}_2\cdot\text{CHO}$ with hydroxy- and methoxybenzoic acids was undertaken in order to compare its behaviour in sulphuric acid condensations with that of chloral.

The condensation of chloral with methoxybenzoic acid has been studied by Fritsch (*Annalen*, 1897, **296**, 358; 1898, **301**, 360), Meldrum (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1911, **99**, 1712), Bargellini and Molina (*Atti R. Accad. Lincei*, 1912, **21**, II, 146) and by Alimehandani and Meldrum (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, **117**, 964); the last mentioned extending their researches to the condensation of chloral with hydroxybenzoic acids (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, **119**, 201).

The general method adopted throughout this work was to dissolve equimolecular amounts of the two substances in sulphuric acid and after twenty four hours to pour the mixture on to ice.

Equimolecular amounts of gallic acid and butylchloral hydrate yielded 3:4:5-trihydroxy-2- $\alpha\alpha\beta$ -trichloropropyl phthalide (I) which corresponds to and reacts in the same manner as the chloral product. It gives a triacetyl compound and the solution in sodium hydroxide turns dark brown in air.

With excess (2 mols.) of butylchloral, (I) is again obtained mixed with (II) which contains four butylchloral groups and which, if Meldrum and Alimehandani's views for the chloral compound (*loc. cit.*) be adopted, can be regarded as containing heterocyclic rings. This compound is insoluble in concentrated sulphuric acid and sodium hydroxide solution, and does not form an acetyl derivative.

The trimethoxy derivative of (I) was difficult to prepare by direct methylation; it was obtained by condensing trimethoxybenzoic acid with butylchloral. For this purpose, 85 p.c. sulphuric

acid was found most suitable; with sulphuric acid of higher concentrations, mixtures of di- and trimethoxy derivatives were obtained. In the corresponding reaction with chloral the dimethoxy derivative only was isolated.

Both the triacetyl- and the trimethoxyphthalides, when reduced with zinc dust and acetic acid give the respective *monochloro* compounds, containing the group $\text{CH}\cdot\text{CCl}:\text{CH}\cdot\text{CH}_3$.

The reduced trimethoxy compound is very stable. It dissolves slowly in caustic soda solution on boiling without change of colour and the original substance is reprecipitated on acidification. It may be assumed that the phthalide ring is opened by alkali and is again closed on acidification. On treatment with sulphuric acid (conc.), the reduction product was not affected.

In the first experiments on the condensation of butylchloral with the three cresotic acids, *diacidic* compounds were obtained; (III) was obtained from the *o*-acid. Meldrum and Alimchandani (*loc. cit.*) isolated a similar compound from the interaction of the acid and chloral. The behaviour of the *p*-acid is thus different from

its behaviour towards chloral with which it gives a heterocyclic ring.

(III)

(IV)

In order to get a simple (1:1) compound, the method was so modified as to yield a slow and continuous current of hydrogen chloride. In this way the *m*-acid yielded easily the compound (IV). It is assumed, in line with Alimchandani and Meldrum's results, that substitution occurs in the *p*-position to the hydroxyl group. From the *o*- and *p*-acids similar compounds were obtained by using excess of butylchloral (2 mols.) and heating the mixture.

EXPERIMENTAL.

3:4:5-Trihydroxy-2- $\alpha\beta$ -trichloropropyl phthalide, (I).—Gallic acid (17 g.) and butylchloral hydrate (19 g.) were dissolved in sulphuric acid (95 p.c.). After 24 hours, the mixture was poured on to ice. The product separated as a spongy mass which slowly became crystalline. It crystallised from acetic acid in colourless prisms, m.p. 260°. (Found: Cl, 32.7. $C_{11}H_9O_5Cl_3$ requires Cl, 32.5 per cent.).

The acetyl derivative crystallises in long needles from methyl alcohol, m.p. 161.62°. (Found: Cl, 23.7. $C_{17}H_{15}O_8Cl_3$ requires Cl, 23.4 per cent.).

Compound (II).—Gallic acid (8.5 g.), butylchloral hydrate (19 g.) and sulphuric acid (100 c.c. 95 p.c.) gave after 24 hours

a white solid. Cold alkali does not dissolve it but changes its colour probably due to decomposition. It crystallises from chloroform in beautiful clusters of needles, m.p. 281-82°. (Found: Cl, 51.7. $C_{23}H_{20}O_6Cl_{12}$ requires Cl, 52.1 per cent.).

3:4:5-Trimethoxy-2- $\alpha\beta$ -trichloropropyl phthalide was prepared by condensing trimethylgallic acid with butyl chloralhydrate. Sulphuric acid of 85 p. c. concentration was found most suitable. With a lower concentration (75 p.c.) the condensation did not proceed at all. With sulphuric acid of 90 p. c. and 100 p. c. concentrations a spongy mass was obtained. It was resolved by successive crystallisation from several organic solvents into syringic acid, its condensation product, (*vide infra*) and the trimethoxy condensation product.

Trimethyl gallic acid (21 g.) and butylchloral hydrate (19 g.) were dissolved in sulphuric acid (85 p.c., 62 c.c.) and the mixture after 10 days. was poured on to ice when a semi-solid mass separated which crystallised from methyl alcohol in transparent plates, m. p. 90-91°. From the methyl alcoholic mother liquor syringic acid and its condensation product were obtained.

3:4:5-Trimethoxy- and 3:4:5-triacetyl-2- α -chloro- α -propylene phthalides were prepared by reducing the corresponding tri-derivatives with Zn dust and acetic acid. It was necessary to warm the mixtures from time to time. Both products were recrystallised from acetone and petroleum ether for analysis.

The trimethoxy compound melts at 110-11°. (Found: Cl, 12.2. $C_{14}H_{15}O_5$ Cl requires Cl, 11.9 per cent.). The triacetyl compound melts at 145°. (Found: Cl, 9.5. $C_{17}H_{15}O_8$ Cl requires Cl, 9.3 per cent.).

The trimethoxy compound dissolves in sodium hydroxide solution (N/10) on boiling, and the original substance is reprecipitated on acidification. Cold sulphuric acid (conc.) dissolves the substance without evolution of HCl gas even on warming and the original substance is obtained on diluting the acid solution. The triacetyl derivative is not so stable.

4-Hydroxy - 3 : 5 - dimethoxy-2- $\alpha\beta$ -trichloropropyl phthalide.—Syringic acid (15 g.), butylchloral hydrate (15 g.) and sulphuric acid (95 p.c. 90 c.c.) were mixed and after 10 days, during which the mixture was warmed from time to time, it was poured on to ice. The solid, separating, was crystallised from benzene and petroleum ether, m. p. 154-55°. (Found: Cl, 30.2. $C_{13}H_{13}O_5Cl_3$, requires Cl, 29.9 per cent.).

The *acetyl derivative* crystallises from absolute alcohol in transparent needles, m. p. 169-70°. (Found: Cl, 27.1. $C_{15}H_{15}O_6Cl_3$ requires Cl, 26.8 per cent.).

$\alpha\alpha\beta$ - *Trichloro-di (3-methyl-4-hydroxy-5-carboxyphenyl) - butane*, (III).—*o*-Cresotic acid (4 g.), butylchloral hydrate (5 g.) and sulphuric acid (sufficient to form a solution) were mixed; after 24 hours the mixture was poured on to ice. The product (III) was crystallised from acetic acid, m. p. 289°. (Found: Cl, 23.0. $C_{20}H_{19}O_6Cl_3$ requires Cl, 23.1 per cent.).

The corresponding *p*- and *m*-compounds were similarly prepared from the respective acids. The *p*-product was crystallised from nitrobenzene and then from acetone and toluene, m. p. 277°. (Found: Cl, 23.3 p.c.). The *m*-product was crystallised from xylene and then from acetic acid in transparent plates, m. p. 298°. (Found: Cl, 23.2 per cent.).

1- $\alpha\beta\beta\beta$ -*Tetrachlorobutyl-2-methylhydroxy-5-benzoic acid*, (IV).—*m*-Cresotic acid (4 g.), butylchloral hydrate (5 g.) and a little coarse sodium chloride were dissolved in sulphuric acid (95 p.c.). More sodium chloride and sulphuric acid were added at intervals. After 24 hours, the mixture was poured on to ice. The product was crystallised from toluene in clusters of needles, m. p. 210°. (Found: Cl, 40.9. $C_{12}H_{12}O_3Cl_4$ requires Cl, 41.0 per cent.).

The corresponding *p*- and *o*-compounds required an excess of butylchloral (2 mols.) and heat. For the former, occasional warming was sufficient, but the preparation of the latter involved heating to 50-60° for 3 days.

The *p*-compound crystallised from benzene in clusters of needles, m. p. 211-12°. (Found: Cl, 40.9 p.c.). The *o*-compound was crystallised from toluene, m. p. 204.05°. (Found: Cl, 40.6 p.c.).

The *o*-acid has a strong tendency to form the diacidic compound which rendered purification difficult.

3- $\alpha\beta\beta\beta$ -*Tetrachloroethyl-5-methyl-6-hydroxybenzoic acid*.—This modified method was also tried with *o*-cresotic acid (1 mol.) chloral hydrate (3 mols.) and sodium chloride and sulphuric acid as before. After 2 days, the mixture was poured on to ice and the product crystallised from carbon tetrachloride, m. p. 184-85°. (Found: Cl, 44.8. $C_{10}H_8O_3Cl_4$ requires Cl, 44.6 per cent.).

